

I Look at the Sky

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People say,

Talking to another person makes the mind lighter.

I say,

Talking to the sky makes the mind lighter.

People say,

A person is their best friend.

I say,

Nature is my best friend.

When I can't find the question,

When the heart cries,

When tears trickle down my eyes,

When I feel like I don't exist,

When life limps forward,

When restlessness arises in pain—

Then,

I look at the sky.

To find answers in my mind,

To wipe away the tears,

I express my pain to the sky.

I look at the sky.

In some unknown stream,
The answer comes to my ear.
A strange calmness arises in my mind,
A blossom of happiness in my eyes.

Then,
I look at the sky.